

Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Performance

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Abstract:

Teachers' job satisfaction is essential to the overall commitment and productivity toward satisfying performance. Job satisfaction is a requirement for the teacher's work performance. In this context, this paper aimed to determine the level of teachers' job satisfaction and performance of the public elementary school teachers in District IV-B, division of Bacolod City, during the school year 2022-2023. Data for this descriptive study was collected from 139 Public Elementary School Teachers who answered a research-made survey instrument. Most teacher-respondents are young, female, have shorter tenure, and have lower educational backgrounds. The level of teachers' job satisfaction has been found to be high. When grouped by age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment, the level of job satisfaction among teachers appears to be high in all areas. When responses were categorized based on length of service and educational attainment, a significant difference was observed in the level of teachers' job satisfaction regarding fringe benefits, working environment, and job responsibilities. However, no significant difference was found in the working environment concerning age groupings and job responsibilities when responses were grouped based on sex. A significant difference in the teachers' level of job performance when grouped according to age, sex, and educational attainment, except in groupings by length of service. Finally, the study found a significant correlation between teachers' job satisfaction and job performance.

Keywords: Teachers' job satisfaction, job performance, fringe benefits, working environment, job responsibilities.

Introduction

Nature of the Problem

The teachers' roles in elementary schools must be supported and considered. Their job satisfaction, so to speak, will help improve and develop the climate of good human relations and workers' job performance. It is for this reason that the technocrats in the Department of Education have continually provided seminar workshops to bolster teachers' skills and knowledge to ensure that every teacher can effectively teach diverse learners, knowledgeable about student learning, competent in complex core academic content, and skillful at the craft of teaching. As Ertürk (2022) stated, the effectiveness and efficiency of the organizations created to achieve certain objectives depend on the care of employees. Creating positive work conditions reveals the importance of humanitarian conception in organizations, ensuring employees' job satisfaction. Creating a positive work environment for teachers, which is essential for schools, will positively impact their job satisfaction and thus improve their performance.

If the teachers are satisfied with their jobs, it will result in good performance and will lead to higher academic achievement of the pupils. In the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), instructional competence is one of the biggest components covering teachers' job performance. Teachers are rated on their IPCRF as Outstanding (4.50-5.00), Very Satisfactory (3.50-4.49), Satisfactory (2.50-3.49), Unsatisfactory (1.50-2.49), and Poor (below 1.49) (Other components include learners' achievement, school home and community involvement and professional and personal characteristics).

By examining the relationship between teachers' job satisfaction, and performance, this study aimed to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of the education system. Being a Teacher III, the researcher has witnessed the ups and downs of the teaching profession in her school. Teachers face higher deliverables and work output but relatively meager pay. This puts into question the commitment of teachers at work. It is a known fact that teachers, if bombarded with heavy loads, extra ancillary work, and extra activity, may affect their productivity at work. Thus, this study seeks to help establish teachers' job satisfaction and performance amid rising workloads and steady pay.

Current State of Knowledge

Organizations always demand greatly performing worker to attain their goal, to provide goods and services they specialize in, and, in turn, to achieve competitive advantage. Job performance refers to the act of completing a given job. Despite no universal definition of job performance, the authors agree that when conceptualizing performance, one must differentiate between an action or behavioral facet and an outcome facet of performance (Wula et al., 2020).

High-performance work systems directly and indirectly influence teachers' in-role performance and extra-role behavior by mediating the quality of working life. Quality of working life is essential to the relationships between high-performance work systems and employees' work behaviors. Structural relationships among learning-organization culture, self-efficacy, work engagement, and job performance in Korean workforce institutions were conducted. Teachers' self-efficacy positively affected their work engagement and job performance, and the relationship between work engagement and job performance was statistically significant. Also identified were the mediating roles of self-efficacy and work engagement in the relationships between the learning-organization culture of workforce-education schools and the teachers' job performance (Song et al., 2018).

There was a difference in the teachers' teaching performance between those teachers teaching in different schools and those teachers teaching in the same school. The basis for promotion and professional development was only the students' test scores, without considering their increased teaching loads. Teachers' autonomy and performance must also be considered to improve the quality of teaching (Wang et al., 2016). However, independence and work-life balance were significantly related to the teachers' job performance, but workload did not contribute to job performance among schoolteachers (Johari et al., 2018). From the research perspective of educational background, the concept of job performance has become increasingly dynamic when researchers have begun to explore the factors contributing to the levels of teachers' job performance, such as leadership.

Accordingly, numerous studies have shown the importance of leadership in teachers' job performance, as leadership is a key quality in achieving excellent performance in education (Hartinah et al., 2020; Saleem et al., 2020; Wachira et al., 2017). As posited by Azainil (2021), school leaders are an essential factor in determining teachers' performance in carrying out their duties and the success of schools in achieving their goals. By identifying and meeting teachers' requirements, school leaders could demonstrate sufficient and practical leadership skills in encouraging teachers to perform more effectively and efficiently. Hence, leadership plays an important role in promoting employees' job performance and in the educational context – teachers.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Teaching is among the most stressful professions in various cultural and educational contexts (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017). Several theories provide us with an understanding of the relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and job performance.

The Equity Theory believes that satisfaction is based on a person's perception of fairness. Applying this theory when conducting a performance appraisal for teachers based on the IPCRF involves balancing the assessment of teachers' contributions to their jobs with the compensation and other rewards associated with their success. A teacher's perception of fairness of his work input and outcome influences his motivation. A teacher typically feels satisfied with the outcome of his effort, including pay, when the compensation matches what he feels he puts into his job. If an employee perceives that others get more for doing less, he typically becomes less motivated to work hard. School Heads create a productive environment by communicating job requirements clearly and establishing fair, consistent performance objectives for all teachers. Attitude strongly predicts behavioral intention, and intention is the antecedent of the actual behavior (Ajzen, 2012).

The amount of dependency on context factors that teachers perceive is a stronger predictor of the intention to teach than their general beliefs about the influence of these factors on teaching. The perceived influence of context factors is more descriptive but needs to be more specific about whether teachers believe and feel these factors play a role in whether they will teach science. Recent research has shown that positive attitude changes in teachers who received additional professional training in science were coupled with a diminishing dependency on external factors and a greater sense of being in control, regardless of the availability of teaching methods, materials, or school support.

These two theories show the role of attitude in effective teaching. Thus, both theories further support and give the researcher an idea of the probable positive relationship of attitude as one of the determinants of teaching performance. When teachers have opportunities for autonomy, receive feedback that enhances their competence, and experience positive relationships with colleagues and students, they are more likely to feel satisfied and motivated, leading to improved job performance.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the teacher's level of job satisfaction and job performance in elementary schools of a district in a medium-sized school division in the central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to determine: 1) the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction in terms of fringe benefits, working environment and job responsibilities; 2) the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 3) teacher's level of job performance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the significant difference in the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 5) the significant difference in the teacher's level of job performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables and; 6) the significant relationship between the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction and their level of job performance.

Research Methodology:

This section discusses the research methodology used, the study's respondents, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

The Descriptive Research Design was used in this study to determine the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction and their level of Performance in a medium-sized school division in the central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Descriptive design is appropriate for studies that aim to determine what prevails in the present condition or relationship, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. The design is a scientific method that involves describing and observing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way (Shuttleworth, 2016). While its primary concerns are conditions and things that exist at the time of the study, it also considers past events and influences that are deemed related to what is being studied in the present.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 139 teachers of the Division with a total population of 216. Since the number of respondents is quite large, stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were used, and the Cochran formula was applied to find the sample size. To get the percentage, the respondents from each district were divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The respondents from each elementary school were randomly selected by the researcher using the lottery technique.

Instruments

The researcher gathered the needed data for this study by constructing a research-made survey questionnaire to determine the level of job satisfaction and their level of performance. It was subjected to validity (4.77-excellent) and reliability (0.886-Acceptable). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good, respectively. This comprised two parts, wherein part I dealt with the profile of respondents in terms of age, sex at birth, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Part II of the questionnaire covered 24 items for Emotional Exhaustion with 8-line items per area.

Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, using a 5-point Likert scale rating with 5 as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely, and 1 as rarely.

The teachers' performance was based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for the School Year 2022-2023.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the research instrument was found valid and reliable, the researcher asked the authority of the Schools Division Superintendent through a letter requesting permission to conduct the study. Upon approval, the researcher set a schedule for the data gathering with a letter of request to the School Principals. The researcher administered and retrieved the research instrument to ensure 100% retrieval. After the retrieval, the data were tallied and tabulated using the proper statistical tools with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) assigned by the statistician.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 utilized the descriptive analytical scheme and the mean to determine the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction according to fringe benefits, Working Environment, and Job Responsibilities. Objective No. 2 utilized the descriptive analytical scheme and the mean to determine the teachers' level of job satisfaction when grouped

according to the aforementioned variables. Objective No. 3 used the descriptive analytical scheme and the mean to determine the teacher's level of job performance during the School Year 2021-2022 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. Objective No. 4 used a comparative analytical scheme and the Mann-Whitney U test that aimed to determine whether or not significant differences exist in the teachers' levels of job satisfaction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Objective No. 5 used a comparative analytical scheme and the Mann-Whitney U test that aimed to determine whether or not significant differences exist in the teachers' levels of job performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Objective 6 utilized relational analytical schemes and the Spearman Rho to determine whether or not a significant relationship exists between the teacher's level of Job Satisfaction and their level of job performance.

Ethical Considerations

The participants' rights were provided, in which they have to understand that their responses will be kept confidential and made available only to the researchers. No one was able to identify the participants when the results were reported, and the participant's name did not appear anywhere in the written report. The participants were made to understand that the consent form was kept separate from the data records to ensure confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study and analyses of these data facilitated by the identified appropriate statistical tools. It interprets the results derived from the analyses.

Table 1
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Fringe Benefits

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Fridge Benefits		
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>		
1. the amount of pay for the work I do...	3.90	High Level
2. the chance to be reclassified/ be promoted	4.17	High Level
3. The benefits I receive are as good as most other organizations can offer.	3.98	High Level
4. when all my efforts are not rewarded the way it should be..	3.87	High Level
5. the way my job provides a secure future	4.19	High Level
6. the way I get full credit for the work I do	4.13	High Level
7. being able to take pride in a job well done.	4.27	High Level
8. the way how my pay compares with that for a similar job in other companies.	4.07	High Level
Overall Mean	4.07	High Level

Table 1 presents teachers' job satisfaction with fringe benefits, with an overall mean score of 4.07, interpreted as "High Level." The highest obtained mean score was 4.27 in item 6, and item 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.87, both interpreted as "High Level." The data imply that teachers demonstrate high job satisfaction, especially regarding fringe benefits. They are content with pay, value professional growth opportunities, and derive pride from their work. This high satisfaction indicates meaningful engagement, fostering a positive work environment. Recognizing teachers' contributions through fair compensation and professional development is crucial for sustaining this satisfaction, fostering motivation, and enhancing educational outcomes. This finding suggests that teachers derive a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment from their work, indicating a strong intrinsic motivation and commitment to their profession. About the findings, Fried et al. (2015) confirmed that one of the aspects that teacher emotions are linked with is their satisfaction with the teaching activity. Also, according to Erarslan (2022) satisfaction is "an enjoyable or pleasurable emotional state which is the result of the valuation of work or employment experiences of a person." In a general sense, job satisfaction is the emotional state, attitude, and appreciation that a person attributes to their job (Crisci et al., 2019).

Table 2
Level of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Area of Work Environment

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Work Environment		
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>		
1. the policies & practices towards employees of the school	4.10	High Level
2. the way my immediate head & I understand each other.	4.25	High Level
3. the spirit of cooperation among my co-workers	4.35	High Level
4. the working conditions (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.)	3.90	High Level
5. the way my co-workers are easy to make friends with	4.31	High Level
6. the way my immediate head trains his/her subordinates.	4.27	High Level
7. the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.24	High Level
8. the way my immediate head takes care of the complaints of his/her employees.	4.40	High Level

Overall Mean

4.23 High Level

Table 2 presents the level of teachers' job satisfaction in work environment results, with an overall average mean score of 4.23, interpreted as "High Level." In the table, item 8 has the highest mean score of 4.40, and item 4 has the lowest mean of 3.90, which is interpreted as "High Level." The overall high mean underscores teachers' positive perceptions of their work environment. The findings suggest widespread positive sentiment across various aspects related to the work environment. Teachers report the highest satisfaction with the way their immediate heads handle complaints. This suggests a strong sense of support and effective communication between teachers and their immediate supervisors, contributing to a positive work environment. This finding indicates that teachers feel supported and heard by their immediate supervisors, which fosters a positive and constructive work environment. When teachers' concerns and grievances are addressed effectively, they enhance their overall job satisfaction and contribute to a more harmonious and productive workplace. While still indicating a high level of satisfaction, the lowest mean is associated with satisfaction with working conditions, including heating, lighting, and ventilation. This may suggest that, while generally content, there could be room for improvement in the physical aspects of the work environment. Teachers' job satisfaction is linked with a number of aspects in educational settings, particularly in the work environment. From the work-related aspect, job satisfaction influences teacher retention, cohesion at school, increasing the status of teaching as a profession; administrative control and organizational culture (Nalipay et al., 2019).

Table 3
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area of Job Responsibilities

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Responsibilities		
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>		
1. the chance to "rub elbows" with important people,	3.82	High Level
2. being able to do things that don't go against my conscience,	3.83	High Level
3. the chance to do work that is well suited to my abilities,	4.35	High Level
4. the chance to tell other co-workers how to do things,	4.12	High Level
5. the chance to try something that makes use of my abilities,	4.35	High Level
6. the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities,	4.39	High Level
7. the chance to develop new and better ways to do the job,	4.49	Very High Level
8. the chance to do things that don't harm my other co-workers,	4.59	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.24	High Level

In the level of teachers' job satisfaction in job responsibilities, an overall mean score of 4.24 was obtained, interpreted as "High Level." The highest mean score of 4.59 was attained by item no. 8, which is interpreted as "Very High Level." And item no 1, got the lowest mean of 3.82, interpreted as "High Level." Overall, the findings from Table 3 suggest a strong positive sentiment across various aspects related to teachers' job responsibilities and highlight teachers' positive perceptions of their job responsibilities. Teachers' satisfaction with the chance to work collaboratively, develop new approaches to their work, and contribute to a positive work environment reflects their dedication to their profession and commitment to continuous improvement and were given an opportunity to perform tasks that don't harm their co-workers. This emphasizes the importance of ethical considerations and collaborative working relationships, contributing to a very high level of job satisfaction. While still indicating high satisfaction, the lowest mean is associated with the chance to "rub elbows" with important people. This suggests that, while not a critical factor, there could be lower satisfaction with opportunities for networking or engaging with influential individuals. In terms of the teaching process, job satisfaction on the part the job responsibilities, teachers contribute to effectiveness and efficiency in teaching, the well-being of both teachers themselves and their students in the classroom environment, teaching competence, quality and job performance as an indicator of student success, school success and overall educational quality (Toropova et al., 2020).

Table 4
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Fringe Benefits According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Fringe Benefits				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the amount of pay for the work I do...	3.73	High Level	4.11	High Level
2. the chance to be reclassified/ be promoted	4.00	High Level	4.37	High Level
3. The benefits I receive are as good as most other organizations can offer.	3.82	High Level	4.16	High Level
4. when all my efforts are not rewarded the way it should be.	3.69	High Level	4.08	High Level

5. the way my job provides a secure future	4.03	High Level	4.39	High Level
6. the way I get full credit for the work I do	3.93	High Level	4.35	High Level
7. being able to take pride in a job well done.	4.08	High Level	4.50	Very High Level
8. the way how my pay compares with that for a similar job in other companies.	3.86	High Level	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	3.89	High Level	4.28	High Level

Table 4 shows the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of Fringe Benefits, when grouped according to their age, garnered an overall mean score of 3.89 from the younger group and 4.28 from the older group, both interpreted as "High Level." The younger group got the highest mean of 4.08 in item 7, and the lowest mean of 3.69 in item 4, and both were interpreted as "high level." In comparison, the older group of teachers got the highest mean of 4.50 in item number 7, interpreted as "very high level," and the lowest mean of 4.08 in item 4, which is interpreted as "High Level." The data on the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of fringe benefits, when grouped by their age, reveals that both younger and older teachers exhibit a "High Level" of job satisfaction; this suggests that both younger and older teachers desire fair recognition and rewards for their hard work and contributions, and when these are not met, it may lead to some level of job dissatisfaction. These results emphasize the importance of recognizing and rewarding teachers' efforts and contributions, regardless of their age. Providing opportunities for career growth and professional development can contribute to teachers' overall job satisfaction, leading to a more motivated and dedicated teaching workforce. Additionally, creating a work environment that values and appreciates the hard work of all teachers can foster a positive and fulfilling teaching experience for educators of all ages (Nalipay et al., 2019).

Table 5
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Working Environment According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Work Environment				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with....</i>				
1. the policies & practices towards employees of the school	4.01	High Level	4.19	High Level
2. the way my immediate head & I understand each other.	4.22	High Level	4.29	High Level
3. the spirit of cooperation among my co-workers	4.27	High Level	4.45	High Level
4. the working conditions (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.)	3.76	High Level	4.06	High Level
5. the way my co-workers are easy to make friends with	4.27	High Level	4.35	High Level
6. the way my immediate head trains his/her subordinates.	4.19	High Level	4.37	High Level
7. the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.19	High Level	4.31	High Level
8. the way my immediate head takes care of the complaints of his/her employees.	4.28	High Level	4.53	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.15	High Level	4.32	High Level

Table 5 shows the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in the area of the working environment when grouped according to their age, garnered an overall mean score of 4.15 from the younger group and 4.32 from the older group, both interpreted as "High Level." The younger group got the highest mean of 4.28 in item 8 and got the lowest mean of 3.76 in item 4, which both interpreted as "high level". Similarly, the older group of teachers had the highest mean of 4.53 in item 8 which is interpreted as "very high level," and the lowest mean of 4.06 in item 4, which is interpreted as "High Level." The data reveals that both younger and older teachers exhibit a "High Level" of job satisfaction; this suggests that both younger and older teachers experience a high level of job satisfaction in the area of working environment. Both groups value the support and responsiveness of their immediate supervisors in addressing their concerns, indicating the significance of strong leadership and effective communication within the workplace. Additionally, the satisfaction with the physical working conditions reflects the importance of providing a conducive and comfortable environment for teachers to carry out their duties. These results emphasize the importance of creating a positive and supportive working environment for all teachers, regardless of their age. Encouraging open communication and addressing employees' concerns can provide teachers with a more satisfying work experience. Furthermore, investing in improving the physical aspects of the working environment can lead to increased job satisfaction and overall well-being among educators (Toropova et al., 2020).

Table 6
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Job Responsibilities According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretatio	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Responsibilities				

	n			
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the chance to "rub elbows" with important people,	3.68	High Level	4.00	High Level
2. being able to do things that don't go against my conscience,	3.66	High Level	4.03	High Level
3. the chance to do work that is well suited to my abilities,	4.24	High Level	4.47	High Level
4. the chance to tell other co-workers how to do things,	4.01	High Level	4.24	High Level
5. the chance to try something that makes use of my abilities,	4.30	High Level	4.40	High Level
6. the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities,	4.35	High Level	4.44	High Level
7. the chance to develop new and better ways to do the job,	4.41	High Level	4.60	Very High Level
8. the chance to do things that don't harm my other co-workers,	4.57	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.15	High Level	4.35	High Level

Table 6 shows the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of job responsibilities when grouped according to their age. It garnered an overall mean score of 4.15 from the younger group and 4.35 from the older group, both interpreted as "High Level." The younger group got the highest mean of 4.57 in item 8, interpreted as "Very High Level," and the lowest mean of 4.01 in item 4. Similarly, the older group of teachers had the highest mean of 4.61 in item number 8, which is interpreted as "very high level," and the lowest mean of 4.0 in item 1, which is interpreted as "High Level." Results reveal that both younger and older teachers exhibit a "High Level" of job satisfaction and highly value the positive and supportive working relationships with their co-teachers and the alignment of their actions with their personal values. These results underscore the importance of promoting a positive and cooperative work culture among all teachers, regardless of their age. Encouraging teamwork and providing opportunities for professional growth can enhance collaboration and job satisfaction among educators. Creating a work environment that allows teachers to uphold their values and ethical standards in their roles can also contribute to a more fulfilling and rewarding teaching experience (Crisci et al., 2019).

Table 7
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Fringe Benefits According to Sex

Area	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Fringe Benefits				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the amount of pay for the work I do...	4.32	High Level	3.75	High Level
2. the chance to be reclassified/ be promoted	4.49	High Level	4.05	High Level
3. The benefits I receive are as good as most other organizations can offer.	4.35	High Level	3.84	High Level
4. when all my efforts are not rewarded the way it should be..	4.41	High Level	3.67	High Level
5. the way my job provides a secured future	4.46	High Level	4.09	High Level
6. the way I get full credit for the work I do	4.51	Very High Level	3.98	High Level
7. being able to take pride in a job well done.	4.46	High Level	4.20	High Level
8. the way how my pay compares with that for a similar job in other companies.	4.49	High Level	3.91	High Level
Overall Mean	4.43	High Level	3.94	High Level

Table 7 shows the extent of teacher's job satisfaction in the area of fringe benefits when grouped according to their sex, garnered an overall mean score of 4.43 from the male group and 3.94 from the female group, both interpreted as "High Level." The male group got the highest mean of 4.51 in item 6,, interpreted as "Very High Level," and the lowest mean of 4.32 in item 1. Meanwhile, the female group of teachers has the highest mean of 4.20 in item number 7 and the lowest mean of 3.67 in item 4, which is interpreted as "High Level". The result shows that both younger and older teachers exhibit a "High Level" of job satisfaction in fringe and benefits. Male teachers find satisfaction in being recognized and rewarded for their work, while female teachers derive fulfillment from the sense of accomplishment in their jobs. These results highlight the importance of recognizing and rewarding the efforts of both male and female teachers in the workplace. Providing equitable opportunities for professional growth, fair credit for their work, and fostering a positive work environment can contribute to all educators' job satisfaction, regardless of gender. (Erarslan, 2022).

Table 8

Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Working Environment According to Sex

Area	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Work Environment				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the policies & practices towards employees of the school	4.19	High Level	4.06	High Level
2. the way my immediate head & I understand each other.	4.27	High Level	4.24	High Level
3. the spirit of cooperation among my co-workers	4.43	High Level	4.32	High Level
4. the working conditions (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.)	4.22	High Level	3.78	High Level
5. the way my co-workers are easy to make friends with	4.43	High Level	4.26	High Level
6. the way my immediate head trains his/her subordinates.	4.35	High Level	4.24	High Level
7. the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.46	High Level	4.16	High Level
8. the way my immediate head takes care of the complaints of his/her employees.	4.62	Very High Level	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level	4.17	High Level

Table 8 shows the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of the working environment when grouped according to their sex. Garnered an overall mean score of 4.37 from the male group and 4.17 from the female group, both interpreted as "High Level." The male group got the highest mean of 4.62 in item 8 which is interpreted as "Very High Level," and got the lowest mean of 4.19 in item 1. The female group of teachers had the highest mean of 4.32 in item number 3, and the lowest mean of 4.06 in item 1, which both interpreted as "High Level." The data reveals that both younger and older teachers exhibit a "High Level" of job satisfaction. Both groups value the support and responsiveness of their immediate supervisors in addressing their concerns, indicating the significance of strong leadership and effective communication within the workplace. These results underscore the importance of creating a positive and supportive working environment for all teachers, regardless of gender. Encouraging open communication and addressing employees' concerns can provide a more satisfying work experience for both male and female teachers. Additionally, providing opportunities for professional development and growth can enhance job satisfaction and overall well-being among educators of all genders. Furthermore, fostering a work culture that values and appreciates the hard work of all teachers can lead to a more positive and fulfilling teaching experience for educators of both sexes (Yan & Lagamayo, 2019).

Table 9

Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Job Responsibilities According to Sex

Area	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Responsibilities				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the chance to "rub elbows" with important people,	4.00	High Level	3.76	High Level
2. being able to do things that don't go against my conscience,	4.05	High Level	3.75	High Level
3. the chance to do work that is well suited to my abilities,	4.41	High Level	4.32	High Level
4. the chance to tell other co-workers how to do things,	4.27	High Level	4.06	High Level
5. the chance to try something that makes use of my abilities,	4.51	Very High Level	4.28	High Level
6. the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities,	4.54	Very High Level	4.33	High Level
7. the chance to develop new and better ways to do the job,	4.70	Very High Level	4.41	High Level
8. the chance to do things that don't harm my other co-workers,	4.73	Very High Level	4.54	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.40	High Level	4.18	High Level

Table 9 shows the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of job responsibilities when grouped according to their sex, garnered an overall mean score of 4.40 from the male group and 4.18 from the female group, both interpreted as "High Level." The male group got the highest mean of 4.73 in item 8, interpreted as "very high level," and got the lowest mean of 4.00 in item 1. The female teachers got the highest mean of 4.54 in item number 8, interpreted as "very high level," and the lowest mean of 3.76 in item 1, which is interpreted as "High Level." Overall, the findings demonstrate that both teachers experience a high level of job satisfaction in the area of job responsibilities. Both groups highly value the chance to work collaboratively and without causing harm to their co-workers. These results highlight Yan & Lagamayo (2019) the importance of promoting a positive and cooperative work culture among all teachers, regardless of gender. Encouraging teamwork, fostering a sense of

camaraderie, and providing opportunities for professional growth can enhance collaboration and job satisfaction among educators of all genders.

Table 10
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Fringe Benefits According to Length of Service

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Fringe Benefits				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with....</i>				
1. the amount of pay for the work I do...	3.72	High Level	4.22	High Level
2. the chance to be reclassified/ be promoted	3.98	High Level	4.49	Very High Level
3. The benefits I receive are as good as most other organizations can offer.	3.81	High Level	4.25	High Level
4. when all my efforts are not rewarded the way it should be.	3.68	High Level	4.18	High Level
5. the way my job provides a secure future	4.01	High Level	4.49	Very High Level
6. the way I get full credit for the work I do	3.95	High Level	4.41	High Level
7. being able to take pride in a job well done.	4.11	High Level	4.55	Very High Level
8. the way how my pay compares with that for a similar job in other companies.	3.88	High Level	4.37	High Level
Overall Mean	3.89	High Level	4.37	High Level

Table 10 shows the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in fringe benefits when grouped according to their length of services, garnered an overall mean score of 3.89 from the shorter group and 4.37 from the longer-tenured group, both interpreted as "High Level." The shorter-tenured group got the highest mean of 4.11 in item 7 and got the lowest mean of 3.68 in item 4, but both were interpreted as "high level." While the longer group of teachers got the highest mean of 4.55 in item number 7, interpreted as "very high level," and the lowest mean of 4.18 in item 4, which was interpreted as "High Level." The data demonstrate that both teachers experience a high level of job satisfaction in fringe benefits. Both groups highly value the fairness and adequacy of their compensation compared to other job opportunities in the market. Although employee retention is a major problem for businesses of all sizes, and many factors contribute to employee retention, compensation is one of the most important. Studies have shown that compensation plays a significant role in employee retention. Employees who are paid more are more likely to stay with their organizations (Sorn, M. K., Fienena, A. R. L., Ali, Y., Rafay, M., & Fu, G., 2023).

Table 11
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Working Environment According to Length of Service

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Work Environment				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with....</i>				
1. the policies & practices towards employees of the school	4.04	High Level	4.20	High Level
2. the way my immediate head & I understand each other.	4.21	High Level	4.31	High Level
3. the spirit of cooperation among my co-workers	4.29	High Level	4.45	High Level
4. the working conditions (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.)	3.78	High Level	4.10	High Level
5. the way my co-workers are easy to make friends with	4.27	High Level	4.37	High Level
6. the way my immediate head trains his/her subordinates.	4.21	High Level	4.37	High Level
7. the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.13	High Level	4.43	High Level
8. the way my immediate head takes care of the complaints of his/her employees.	4.31	High Level	4.55	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.15	High Level	4.35	High Level

Table 11 presents the results on the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of working environment, grouped according to their length of service. The general mean score for teachers with a shorter length of service is 4.15 and for higher is 4.35 which both exhibit a high level of job satisfaction in the area of working environment. For both categories, the highest mean indicators at 4.31 and 4.55, for item no.8, respectively, reveal that they are highly satisfied with how their immediate head takes care of the complaints and concerns of their employees. This finding demonstrates that both teachers experience a high level of job satisfaction and value the support and responsiveness of their immediate supervisors in addressing their concerns, which also contributes to a positive and supportive work environment. These results highlight the importance of effective leadership and

communication in promoting a positive working environment for teachers at all stages of their careers. Encouraging open communication and addressing employees' concerns can provide a more satisfying work experience for newer and more experienced teachers. Fostering a supportive work culture that values employee feedback and well-being can lead to a more fulfilling and rewarding teaching experience for educators of all lengths of service (Luthra, 2015).

Table 12
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Job Responsibilities According to Length of Service

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Responsibilities				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the chance to "rub elbows" with important people,	3.72	High Level	4.00	High Level
2. being able to do things that don't go against my conscience,	3.68	High Level	4.08	High Level
3. the chance to do work that is well suited to my abilities,	4.26	High Level	4.49	Very High Level
4. the chance to tell other co-workers how to do things,	4.04	High Level	4.25	High Level
5. the chance to try something that makes use of my abilities,	4.29	High Level	4.43	High Level
6. the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities,	4.34	High Level	4.47	High Level
7. the chance to develop new and better ways to do the job,	4.41	High Level	4.63	Very High Level
8. the chance to do things that don't harm my other co-workers,	4.58	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.16	High Level	4.37	High Level

Table 12 presents the results on the level of teachers' job satisfaction in job responsibilities when grouped according to their length of service. The overall mean score for teachers with a shorter length of service is 4.16 and 4.37 for longer, both of which exhibit a high level of job satisfaction. For both categories, the highest mean indicators at 4.58 and 4.61, respectively, reveal that they are highly satisfied with their chance to do things that don't harm other workers. This finding suggests that both teachers are committed to maintaining a positive and harmonious work environment where they can collaborate effectively without causing harm to their colleagues. These results emphasize the significance of promoting a collaborative and considerate work environment among all teachers, regardless of their length of service. Encouraging teamwork, fostering a sense of camaraderie, and providing opportunities for professional growth can enhance collaboration and job satisfaction among educators of all experience levels. Additionally, recognizing and appreciating the efforts of teachers in maintaining a harmonious work atmosphere can lead to a more fulfilling and rewarding teaching experience for both newer and more experienced educators (Lopes & Oliveria, 2017).

Table 13
Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Fringe Benefits According to Highest Educational Attainment

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Fringe Benefits				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with...</i>				
1. the amount of pay for the work I do...	3.69	High Level	4.22	High Level
2. the chance to be reclassified/ be promoted	3.99	High Level	4.44	High Level
3. The benefits I receive are as good as most other organizations can offer.	3.75	High Level	4.31	High Level
4. when all my efforts are not rewarded the way it should be..	3.62	High Level	4.24	High Level
5. the way my job provides a secure future	4.05	High Level	4.40	High Level
6. the way I get full credit for the work I do	3.85	High Level	4.53	Very High Level
7. being able to take pride in a job well done.	4.09	High Level	4.55	Very High Level
8. the way how my pay compares with that for a similar job in other companies.	3.89	High Level	4.33	High Level
Overall Mean	3.86	High Level	4.38	High Level

Table 13 presents the results on the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of fringe benefits, grouped according to their highest educational attainment (HEA). The general mean score for teachers with lower HEA is 3.86, and for higher group at 4.38 both categories of teachers exhibit a high level of job satisfaction in the area of fringe benefits. For both categories, the highest mean indicators at 4.09 and 4.55, respectively, reveal that they are highly satisfied with taking pride in a job well done. This finding suggests that teachers with lower and

higher educational attainment derive a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment from their work, which contributes significantly to their overall job satisfaction in fringe benefits. Providing professional growth and advancement opportunities and fostering a supportive work environment can contribute to higher job satisfaction among educators of all educational attainment levels. Additionally, offering competitive and fair compensation packages can further enhance job satisfaction and motivation among teachers, encouraging them to continue striving for excellence in their profession (Jongil, Y., & Choi, S. (2017).

Table 14

Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Working Environment According to Highest Educational Attainment

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Work Environment				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with....</i>				
1. the policies & practices towards employees of the school	3.96	High Level	4.29	High Level
2. the way my immediate head & I understand each other.	4.14	High Level	4.42	High Level
3. the spirit of cooperation among my co-workers	4.23	High Level	4.53	Very High Level
4. the working conditions (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.)	3.74	High Level	4.13	High Level
5. the way my co-workers are easy to make friends with	4.20	High Level	4.47	High Level
6. the way my immediate head trains his/her subordinates.	4.12	High Level	4.49	Very High Level
7. the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.10	High Level	4.45	High Level
8. the way my immediate head takes care of the complaints of his/her employees.	4.27	High Level	4.58	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.10	High Level	4.42	High Level

Table 14 presents the results on the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of working environment, grouped according to their highest educational attainment. The general mean score for teachers with lower educational attainment is 4.10, while the higher group is 4.42, and both categories of teachers exhibit a high level of job satisfaction in the working environment. For both categories, the highest mean indicators at 4.10 and 4.42, respectively, reveal that they are highly satisfied with how their immediate head takes care of their employees' complaints. This finding suggests that both teachers feel supported and valued by their superiors regardless of their educational attainment. Both groups highly value the support and responsiveness they receive from their immediate supervisors or heads when addressing their concerns or issues in the workplace. These results underscore the significance of effective leadership and management in creating a positive and supportive work environment for all teachers. Encouraging open communication, actively listening to teachers' feedback, and addressing their needs can foster a sense of trust and satisfaction among educators. Furthermore, providing opportunities for professional development and growth can contribute to a more fulfilling and engaging work environment, enhancing overall job satisfaction among teachers (Luthra, 2015).

Table 15

Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Job Responsibilities According to Highest Educational Attainment

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Job Responsibilities				
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with....</i>				
1. the chance to "rub elbows" with important people,	3.73	High Level	3.96	High Level
2. being able to do things that don't go against my conscience,	3.68	High Level	4.05	High Level
3. the chance to do work that is well suited to my abilities,	4.20	High Level	4.56	Very High Level
4. the chance to tell other co-workers how to do things,	3.99	High Level	4.31	High Level
5. the chance to try something that makes use of my abilities,	4.22	High Level	4.53	Very High Level
6. the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities,	4.27	High Level	4.56	Very High Level
7. the chance to develop new and better ways to do the job,	4.37	High Level	4.67	Very High Level
8. the chance to do things that don't harm my other co-workers,	4.44	High Level	4.80	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.11	High Level	4.43	High Level

Table 15 presents the results on the level of teachers' job satisfaction in job responsibilities, grouped according to their highest educational attainment. The general mean score for teachers with lower educational attainment is 4.11. For those with higher attainment, it is 4.43, which exhibits a high level of job satisfaction in job responsibilities. For both categories, the highest mean indicators at 4.44 and 4.80, respectively, reveal they are very satisfied with the chance to do things that don't harm other co-workers. This finding suggests that teachers feel empowered to carry out their job responsibilities without negatively affecting their colleagues. They clearly understand their roles and responsibilities and feel supported in fulfilling them effectively. The higher mean score among teachers with higher educational attainment may be attributed to their advanced knowledge and skills acquired through their additional education. This may allow them to navigate their job responsibilities more confidently, leading to a higher level of job satisfaction and feel content with the opportunity to carry out their duties which suggests a positive and supportive work environment. Creating a work environment that values cooperation and teamwork can contribute to a higher level of job satisfaction among educators. Additionally, ongoing professional development opportunities can help teachers enhance their skills and competencies, leading to a greater sense of fulfillment in their roles. Recognizing and rewarding teachers for their efforts and achievements can further boost their job satisfaction and overall motivation to excel in their profession (Torres, 2019).

Table 16
Difference in the Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Fringe and Benefits when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	59.68	1641.000	0.004	0.05	Significant
	Older	63	79.03				
Sex	Male	38	85.61	1198.500	0.002	0.05	Significant
	Female	101	62.11				
Length of Service	Shorter	87	59.36	1390.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Longer	52	83.74				
Educational Attainment	Lower	83	57.04	1299.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Higher	56	85.37				

Table 16 presents the findings on the difference in the level of teachers' job satisfaction in fringe benefits when grouped and compared according to age, sex, length of service, and highest educational attainment, and results show "significant." The results suggest that these variables significantly influence the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of fringe benefits. Older teachers, females, those with longer lengths of service, and those with higher educational attainments tend to experience higher job satisfaction in terms of fringe benefits compared to their counterparts. According to Sharma and Jyoti (2016), factors affecting a teacher's job satisfaction encompass internal and external elements, demographic factors, and individual characteristics of both the teacher and the school. Teachers' job satisfaction is influenced by external factors such as school and principal characteristics and internal factors such as the teacher's own characteristics. Understanding the interplay of these factors is essential for crafting strategies to enhance job satisfaction among educators, ultimately contributing to a more positive and productive teaching environment. Recognizing the nuanced dynamics of job satisfaction can guide educational institutions and policymakers in creating supportive and fulfilling workplaces for teachers.

Table 17
Difference in the Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area Working Environment when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	62.77	1870.000	0.062	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	63	75.34				
Sex	Male	38	79.91	1409.500	0.038	0.05	Significant
	Female	101	64.24				
Length of Service	Shorter	87	62.61	1667.000	0.024	0.05	Significant
	Longer	52	78.31				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	83	57.36	1325.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Higher	56	84.91				

Table 17 reveals that gender, length of service, and highest educational attainment significantly influence the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of working environment. However, age does not have a significant impact on teachers' job satisfaction regarding the working environment. In related studies, Kinman et al. (2012) found a positive relationship between teaching experience and job satisfaction in a study involving 628 teachers in secondary schools in the UK. Conversely, Van Maele and Van Houtte (2012) discovered a negative relationship between job satisfaction and seniority in their analysis of 2091 teachers in 80 secondary schools in Belgium. Another study conducted in Taiwan with 135 teachers by Cheng and Ren (2010) concluded that the level of education is an important determinant of job satisfaction. These findings collectively highlight the complex interplay of factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction, encompassing gender, length of service, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, seniority, and level of education. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for educational institutions and policymakers to formulate targeted interventions and create supportive working environments that enhance overall job satisfaction among teachers.

Table 18
Difference in the Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction in the Area of Job Responsibilities when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	60.66	1714.000	0.011		Significant
	Older	63	77.85				
Sex	Male	38	78.15	1474.500	0.080		Not Significant
	Female	101	64.89				
Length of Service	Shorter	87	62.12	1625.500	0.014	0.05	Significant
	Longer	52	79.13				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	83	58.10	1385.000	0.000		Significant
	Higher	56	83.82				

Results from Table 18 suggest that age, length of service, and highest educational attainment significantly influence the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the area of job responsibilities. However, gender does not significantly impact teachers' job satisfaction regarding their job responsibilities. In support of these findings, Shrestha (2019) conducted a study involving 345 teachers, concluding that older teachers tend to display higher job satisfaction, leading to increased commitment and higher job performance. Additionally, Masath (2015) explored the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers across different age groups, noting an increasing dissatisfaction among young teachers. To address this issue, the study suggested implementing orientation activities and forming organizations led by teacher-educators to better prepare young teachers for the profession.

Table 19
Difference in the Level of Teacher's Job Performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	65.27	2055.000	0.002		Significant
	Older	63	72.35				
Sex	Male	38	63.04	1629.500	0.000		Significant
	Female	101	70.54				
Length of Service	Shorter	87	64.32	1812.500	0.109	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	52	75.46				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	83	66.76	2086.500	0.000		Significant
	Higher	56	71.06				

Results from Table 19 suggest that age, gender, and highest educational attainment significantly influence the level of teachers' job satisfaction. However, job satisfaction is the same based on length of service. This also indicates that except for length of service these variables significantly influence the level of teachers' job satisfaction. In line with these findings, a study by Gu and Wang (2017) emphasizes the impact of various factors on teachers' job satisfaction. According to their research, elements such as organization system, reputation, working conditions, career development, and salary play pivotal roles in determining teacher satisfaction. Importantly, the study notes that male teachers are more satisfied with career development than their female counterparts. These insights underscore the multifaceted nature of job satisfaction in the teaching profession, influenced by organizational, personal, and gender-related factors. Recognizing the specific aspects contributing to

job satisfaction is crucial for educational institutions and policymakers in devising strategies to enhance overall job satisfaction among teachers. Understanding these dynamics can lead to targeted interventions that address the unique needs and concerns of different demographic groups within the teaching workforce.

Table 20
Relationship between the Levels of Teacher's Job Satisfaction and Job Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of Job Satisfaction	1.000	0.012	0.05	Significant
Level of Work Performance				

Table 20 presents that there is a significant relationship between the level of teachers' job satisfaction and the level of job performance. Results indicate that some school principals needed to fulfill their expected responsibilities, deviating from their job descriptions and delegating their roles to teachers. There were variations in performance, with some being recognized as high achievers while others were considered poor performers. Classroom observation by principals varied, with some regularly visiting classes and others rarely doing so. The focus of some principals on allocating resources for school beautification was noted, sometimes at the expense of their primary role—ensuring the delivery of quality education by closely monitoring teachers and ensuring competencies in all subject areas were covered and accomplished (Lincuna & Caingcoy, 2020). These findings highlight the interconnectedness between principals' actions, teachers' job satisfaction, and the subsequent impact on overall job performance. Addressing these issues in school leadership and management is crucial to fostering a positive and effective educational environment.

Conclusions

The research environment is manned by teachers with limited pedagogical experience but with the potential for a unique educational perspective. The high level of job satisfaction among teacher-respondents is a positive indicator for the well-being of both educators and students and suggests a healthy work environment, positive teacher-student interactions, and a commitment to excellence in education. And results shows significant relationship between the Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction and the Level of Job Performance. These findings highlight the interconnectedness between principals' actions, teachers' job satisfaction, and the subsequent impact on overall job performance. Addressing these issues in school leadership and management is crucial to fostering a positive and effective educational environment. In the light of the findings and conclusions derived from the study, the following recommendations and plan of action were formulated: 1) Provide targeted support and professional development opportunities to younger and less experienced teachers to enhance their skills and job satisfaction; 2) Continue fostering a positive work environment, providing attractive fringe benefits, and recognizing and valuing the importance of teachers' job responsibilities to further enhance and maintain their overall job satisfaction and well-being; 3) Continue to prioritize and maintain positive work environments, offer attractive fringe benefits, and provide meaningful job responsibilities to enhance teachers' job satisfaction further; 4) Continue to prioritize and support professional development opportunities for teachers; 5) Consider teachers' length of service and educational attainment when addressing job satisfaction concerns related to fringe and benefits, working environment, and job responsibilities and 6) Consider age, sex, and educational attainment as important factors in addressing teachers' job performance.

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